

Understanding the Physics of Trajectory of 2002 VE68 - A Review Paper

Shobhini Khanna

DPS RK Puram, New Delhi, India

Shobhinikhanna24@gmail.com

Abstract

Asteroids are rocky bodies of the size of a few meters to hundred of kilometers in size. An interesting phenomenon is observed for asteroid 2002 VE68 whose orbital time period of the asteroid around the sun is close to the orbital time period of Venus, this is known as 1:1 mean resonance. In this case, it resembles as if the asteroid is a natural satellite of Venus, but in reality it is not, thus this satellite is known as quasi-satellite or quasi-moon of Venus. In this paper the trajectory of the asteroid is studied by following two main papers by Mikkola, Marcos and Marcos. Simulations are created in both these papers, by considering the effect of Sun, Venus and other planets, major dwarf planets on the asteroid, and different models are created. The simulations of Mikkola, and Marcos and Marcos suggest that the asteroid is a part of its orbit for more than 7000 years ago and will be for another 500 years, before getting ejected out of its orbit.

Introduction

Asteroids, the ancient wanderers of our solar system, are like cosmic nomads, traveling endlessly in their solitary orbits around the Sun. These rocky bodies, some no bigger than a pebble and others stretching hundreds of kilometers, come in all shapes—jagged, irregular, and far from the perfect spheres we often associate with celestial bodies. Most are found between Mars and Jupiter, forming a sprawling highway of debris known as the asteroid belt, a chaotic dance floor where millions of these objects spin and tumble, pulled by the gravitational rhythms of both the mighty Sun and the distant planets. But asteroids aren't limited to this one region; they scatter across the solar system, their paths dictated by an intricate web of forces. They are composed of rock and metal, the ancient building blocks left over from the formation of planets, and sometimes bear traces of more exotic materials, like carbon and silica, hidden within their cores. These frozen relics offer a glimpse into the distant past, like messengers carrying the secrets of our solar system's birth [1].

A truly remarkable phenomenon occurs when an asteroid's journey through space aligns almost perfectly with that of a planet. When its orbit syncs up just right, the asteroid seems to follow the planet like a shadow, as if tethered to its gravitational pull. But here's the twist—this asteroid

isn't a moon, at least not in the traditional sense. It isn't bound to the planet directly, but rather, it moves in a delicate, synchronized ballet with both the planet and the Sun. This curious phenomenon is known as a "quasi-orbit," and these celestial companions are called "quasi-moons." Quasi-moons are the solar system's drifters, objects that seem to hover near a planet, yet remain free, never fully captured by its gravity. Picture them as cosmic dance partners, moving in step with a planet across the solar stage, but always just out of reach. The Sun, ever the master choreographer, ensures that the quasi-moon's orbit aligns just enough to give the appearance of a close relationship, when in reality, the asteroid is in a delicate balancing act, influenced equally by the Sun's gravitational embrace and the planet's pull.

Take Earth, for example. It has five such cosmic companions—3753 Cruithne, 2003 YN107, 2004 GU9, 2006 FV35, and SO16. These asteroids, like quiet observers, trace Earth's path around the Sun, never straying too far, but never truly settling into Earth's orbit like our familiar Moon. Their paths are intricate, looping patterns that trace invisible lines of gravitational force, a testament to the complex interactions that govern our solar system. Jupiter, the gas giant, also boasts a handful of quasi-moons—2001 QQ199, 2004 AE9, P/2002 AR2, and P/2003 WC7—each one a traveler in its own right, dancing to the rhythm of both Jupiter's massive gravitational field and the Sun's powerful influence. These quasi-moons are like cosmic nomads, choosing to stay close to their planetary partners but never fully committing to becoming moons.

Even Venus has a lone quasi-moon, 2002 VE68, the first of its kind to be discovered. This asteroid's path weaves through space in a delicate interplay between the Sun and Venus, a graceful reminder of how dynamic and fluid the universe truly is. Quasi-moons, with their strange and mysterious orbits, embody the delicate dance of gravity and motion. They are not prisoners of the planets they follow, but rather free spirits, drifting on cosmic winds, forever sharing space yet maintaining their distance. Their orbits remind us that the universe is not rigid and static, but alive with motion, rhythm, and subtle connections that bind even the smallest of celestial bodies in an eternal, graceful dance through the cosmos.

Discussion

In 2002, astronomer Seppo Mikkola from Finland's Tuorla Observatory made a fascinating discovery regarding an asteroid designated as 2002 VE68. Though the Lowell Observatory had detected this asteroid, Mikkola's observations led to deeper insights into its unique orbital behavior. The asteroid shares an intriguing relationship with Venus, with an orbital period around the Sun of about 225 days—remarkably close to the orbital period of Venus itself. This similarity in orbital periods gives the illusion, from the perspective of Venus, that the asteroid is orbiting the planet, making it appear as though it is a natural satellite. However, this is not the case. In reality, 2002 VE68, like other quasi-moons, is not bound to Venus but to the Sun, following a

path that closely mimics Venus' orbit. This peculiar celestial relationship is what earns such objects the title of "quasi-moons."

When studying the dynamics of co-orbital objects like 2002 VE68, astronomers recognize three distinct types of orbital trajectories: tadpole motion, horseshoe motion, and retrograde quasi-satellite motion. These trajectories are defined by the gravitational forces acting on the object and its relative position to the planet and the Sun. In the case of 2002 VE68, Mikkola and his team's theoretical studies and numerical simulations revealed that it follows a retrograde quasi-satellite motion, a type of orbital path in which the asteroid appears to orbit Venus, but in a counterclockwise (retrograde) direction relative to the planet's orbit. This makes 2002 VE68 the first asteroid to be discovered with such a trajectory, marking a significant milestone in the understanding of quasi-moons and co-orbital dynamics.

To further investigate this asteroid's motion, numerical experiments were conducted using observed orbital data collected from the Lowell Observatory. These simulations helped to predict the trajectory of 2002 VE68, revealing critical orbital parameters (listed in the table from the original study) that define its unique motion around the Sun in close synchrony with Venus. These findings have enriched our understanding of how quasi-moons behave and how complex gravitational interactions can lead to such extraordinary orbital dynamics.

a (AU)	e	i	Ω	ω	M
0.72368	0.4104	8.9766	231.674	355.528	318.875

Table No 1

In addition to analyzing the current trajectory of the asteroid 2002 VE68, computer simulations were employed to project its path over the next 150 years. The simulations provide a detailed look at how the asteroid's orbit will evolve, offering insight into the long-term stability of its quasi-moon status.

As shown in figure 1, the trajectory is illustrated in a rotating coordinate system, which is centered on Venus. This perspective, where Venus remains stationary, helps visualize how 2002 VE68 appears to orbit around the planet, even though it is not gravitationally bound to it. The rotating frame effectively isolates the asteroid's motion relative to Venus, highlighting the retrograde quasi-satellite motion that was first identified through theoretical work by Seppo Mikkola.

Over the course of the simulation, the asteroid traces out a complex looping pattern around Venus, never fully settling into a traditional orbit but remaining close to the planet in its

quasi-moon relationship. These projections are critical for understanding the asteroid's future interactions with both Venus and other solar system bodies, as small perturbations from other planets or the Sun could eventually alter its trajectory. However, for at least the next century and a half, 2022 VE68 is expected to maintain this fascinating co-orbital behavior, continuing its dance with Venus while remaining firmly in orbit around the Sun.

This simulation not only underscores the stability of its current path but also adds to the broader understanding of how quasi-moons like 2022 VE68 interact with their planetary companions over long time scales. It offers a glimpse into the delicate gravitational balances that govern the motion of such bodies within the dynamic environment of the solar system.

Figure No 1: The motion of 2022 VE68 for the next 150 years.

Figure 2: The distance of the asteroid from the Earth

The paper concludes with a significant discovery: the existence of Venus's quasi-satellite, officially named 2002 VE68. This asteroid has likely been in its current orbit for approximately 7,000 years and, according to simulations, will remain there for another 500 years or possibly longer. Despite its long-term stability, another key finding is that 2002 VE68 could eventually be ejected from its orbit. The study also suggests an intriguing possibility: the asteroid may have been inserted into its current orbit by a gravitational interaction with Earth, indicating a complex dynamical history that involves multiple planets.

In a second study, by researchers C. de la Fuente Marcos and R. de la Fuente Marcos - referred to here as Marcos and Marcos - the focus shifts to the dynamical evolution of 2002 VE68. This paper provides additional insights into the asteroid's behavior and orbital characteristics. Discovered by astronomer Brian Skiff of the Lowell Observatory's LONEOS survey on November 11, 2002, the asteroid's semimajor axis was measured at 0.7237 AU, nearly identical to Venus's orbital distance from the Sun. Its eccentricity was found to be 0.4104, which adds to the complexity of its orbital path, contributing to its designation as a potentially hazardous asteroid by the Minor Planet Center.

The research by Marcos and Marcos highlights that 2002 VE68's orbit is not entirely stable, due to perturbations caused by the gravitational influences of Mercury, Venus, and Earth. Its highly eccentric orbit makes it particularly sensitive to these perturbations, introducing the possibility of significant future shifts in its trajectory. Despite this instability, the asteroid maintains a 1:1 mean motion resonance with Venus, meaning that its orbital period matches that of the planet. From the vantage point of Venus, the asteroid appears to orbit the planet, creating the illusion of a true moon, though it remains an independent object in orbit around the Sun. The simulations conducted by Marcos and Marcos, depicted in figure 4, confirm this quasi-satellite behavior and provide detailed trajectory parameters, summarized in table 2. These simulations further illustrate the asteroid's long-term resonance with Venus and its interactions with other planetary bodies, which contribute to its evolving path. The continued study of 2002 VE68 offers a fascinating glimpse into the delicate gravitational balances that shape the orbits of small bodies within the solar system and the potential for future changes in its status as a quasi-moon.

Figure 4: Trajectory of the asteroid with respect to the Sun's frame of reference. The motion is plotted for 150 years.

a (AU)	e	i	Ω	ω	M
0.7236	0.4103	9.005	231.584	355.463	202.88

Table No 2:

In their study, Marcos and Marcos examined the dynamical evolution of asteroid 2002 VE68 through three different models, each exploring the effects of various gravitational perturbations.

Model 1 focuses on the perturbation of the asteroid's orbit by eight major planets in the solar system. The simulations reveal that the asteroid's trajectory is inherently unstable, with its orbital elements - such as the semimajor axis, eccentricity, and inclination - fluctuating significantly over time, as shown in figure 5. These orbital parameters highlight the chaotic nature of its motion, especially as it moves between different orbital regimes.

Key findings from Model 1:

- 1) **Perturbation by Major Planets:** The orbit of 2002 VE68 is heavily influenced by the gravitational effects of the major planets. Its path is particularly sensitive to the positions of these planets, causing frequent transitions between different types of co-orbital motion.
- 2) **Lagrangian Points and Orbital Shifts:** The asteroid alternates between occupying the L5 Trojan and L4 Trojan positions relative to Venus, as well as transitioning into a

horseshoe orbit and, at times, becoming a quasi-satellite. These transitions mark significant changes in its behavior, demonstrating how the object is dynamically “tossed” between these stable regions due to gravitational perturbations. The horseshoe orbit is characterized by a loop-like trajectory around Venus, while the quasi-satellite motion mimics a bound orbit, though the asteroid remains gravitationally tied to the Sun.

- 3) **High Eccentricity and Instability:** Throughout these shifts in motion, the asteroid exhibits high eccentricity, meaning its orbit is elongated rather than circular. This eccentricity fluctuates, especially when the object moves from the L5 Lagrangian point (behind Venus) to the L4 point (ahead of Venus in its orbit). The variation in eccentricity reflects the gravitational tug-of-war between Venus, Earth, and the Sun.
- 4) **Close Interaction with Earth:** Approximately 11,000 years ago, the asteroid had a close encounter with Earth, passing at a distance of about 0.007 AU (astronomical units). This interaction injected the asteroid into its current quasi-satellite orbit around Venus. Earth’s gravitational influence played a crucial role in placing 2002 VE68 into its current trajectory, demonstrating the significant impact that close planetary encounters can have on small bodies.
- 5) **Dominant Perturbations by Earth and Mercury:** The resonance behavior of the asteroid is primarily controlled by Earth's gravitational pull. Mercury also exerts a minor influence on the asteroid’s trajectory, though its effect is comparatively small.
- 6) **Ejection from Orbit:** Despite its current quasi-satellite status, simulations predict that 2002 VE68 will eventually be ejected from this orbit. The asteroid’s instability will cause it to leave its quasi-satellite orbit after roughly 5,000 years, likely due to ongoing perturbations from Earth or other inner planets.

In summary, **Model 1** reveals that 2002 VE68's orbit is highly dynamic and unstable, with significant gravitational interactions governing its movement between various co-orbital configurations. Its current quasi-satellite status around Venus was established after a close encounter with Earth thousands of years ago, but its future remains uncertain, as it is expected to be ejected from this orbit in several millennia

Figure No 5: semimajor axis, eccentricity and inclination

From the image (figure 5), we can observe a significant shift in the asteroid 2002 VE68's orbital parameters over time, particularly around the 10,000-year mark. At this point, the semi-major axis distance, which represents the average distance of the asteroid from the Sun, experiences a sharp increase. This indicates that the asteroid will begin to move farther away from its current orbit. Simultaneously, there is a sharp decrease in the asteroid's eccentricity, which makes the orbit more circular. This transition suggests that while the asteroid is moving away from its quasi-satellite state, its trajectory is becoming more stable and less elongated, transitioning from the highly eccentric, unstable orbit it currently occupies.

In addition to these changes, the inclination of the asteroid's orbit, which measures the tilt of the orbit relative to the plane of the solar system, will also increase. This change in inclination reflects a dynamic alteration in the asteroid's overall path, as it gradually evolves from a quasi-satellite to a different orbital state. These orbital changes culminate in a major transition after about 500 years. At this point, 2002 VE68 is expected to leave its quasi-satellite orbit around Venus and evolve into a passing object. No longer bound in a quasi-moon relationship, the asteroid will continue to orbit the Sun but will pass by Venus periodically, no longer mimicking a moon's motion. This transition marks the beginning of a new phase in the asteroid's evolution, as gravitational perturbations continue to shape its trajectory.

Model 2 builds upon the findings of **Model 1** by incorporating the gravitational influence of the Moon, alongside the eight major planets. This adjustment allows for a more precise understanding of the asteroid 2002 VE68's orbital behavior, particularly during close encounters with Earth.

Key findings from Model 2 :

1. Moon's Influence: While Model 1 projected that 2002 VE68 would come as close to Earth as 0.002 AU (which is closer than the Moon), Model 2 includes the Moon's gravitational effects. This consideration adds complexity to the system, as the asteroid's close approach to Earth would be further influenced by the Moon's gravitational field. These interactions could slightly alter the asteroid's path during these close encounters, adding an additional layer of dynamics to the system.

2. Revised Timeline: In contrast to Model 1, which suggested that the asteroid entered its quasi-satellite phase around 11,000 years ago, Model 2's simulations suggest that 2002 VE68 actually became a quasi-satellite around 7,000 years ago. This revision in timing highlights the impact that including the Moon's gravitational effects can have on refining the asteroid's past dynamical behavior.

3. Close Encounters with Mercury and Earth: Both models reveal close interactions between 2002 VE68 and Earth, but Model 2 also suggests that Mercury plays a more prominent role in influencing the asteroid's orbit. Close encounters of about 0.0025 AU are projected with both Earth and Mercury, indicating that the resonance behavior of the asteroid is controlled by the gravitational influence of both planets. These encounters, occurring periodically, help maintain the asteroid's 1:1 resonance with Venus, but also add to its long-term instability.

4. Venus Encounters: Interestingly, the simulations show that relatively close encounters with Venus - distances under 0.03 AU - occurred primarily before 2002 VE68 entered its quasi-satellite phase. This suggests that Venus's gravitational influence may have played a role in setting up the asteroid's current orbit. Once in the quasi-satellite phase, however, the asteroid no longer comes close to Venus. After it leaves the quasi-satellite state, close encounters with Venus (around 0.013 AU) are expected again, marking a new phase in its orbital evolution.

In summary, **Model 2** introduces the Moon's perturbation into the asteroid's dynamical analysis, refining the timeline of when 2002 VE68 became a quasi-satellite and identifying more nuanced interactions with Mercury and Earth. It also suggests that the asteroid's resonant behavior is jointly controlled by Earth and Mercury, with Venus playing a role primarily before and after the quasi-satellite phase. This model provides a more comprehensive picture of the asteroid's orbital evolution and the complex gravitational forces shaping its trajectory.

Model 2 refines the dynamical analysis of asteroid 2002 VE68 by accounting for the perturbative effects of both the Moon and eight major planets. This model focuses on the close encounters of the asteroid with Earth and other celestial bodies, providing a deeper understanding of the asteroid's evolution as a quasi-satellite.

Key Findings from Model 2:

1. Close Encounters with Earth and the Moon: One of the most significant observations is the asteroid's close encounter with Earth at a distance of just 0.002 AU, which is even smaller than the average distance between Earth and the Moon (~0.00257 AU). This proximity means that Earth's Moon also plays an important role in perturbing the asteroid's orbit. The gravitational influence of the Moon adds complexity to the asteroid's trajectory, introducing small but significant variations that can alter its path and long-term stability.

2. Perturbations from Mercury and Earth: In addition to Earth, Mercury also plays a significant role in shaping the orbit of 2002 VE68. The asteroid comes as close as 0.0025 AU to both Earth and Mercury, making these two planets the primary sources of perturbation. These close encounters indicate that the gravitational effects of Earth and Mercury are key in controlling the resonance behavior of the asteroid as it continues its quasi-satellite orbit around Venus.

3. No Close Encounters with Venus in Quasi-Satellite Phase: Notably, while Venus is the central planet around which the asteroid exhibits quasi-satellite behavior, there are no close encounters between 2002 VE68 and Venus while it is in the quasi-satellite phase. This suggests that the gravitational influence of Venus is more subtle, exerting control from a distance, rather than through close interactions. Venus's perturbative influence is likely more important before the asteroid enters the quasi-satellite phase and after it exits.

4. Quasi-Satellite Status for 7,000 Years: According to Model 2, the asteroid has been in its quasi-satellite orbit for approximately 7,000 years, a revision from the earlier estimate of 11,000 years in Model 1. This adjustment in the timeline highlights the sensitivity of the asteroid's evolution to minor gravitational perturbations, such as those introduced by the Moon.

In summary, **Model 2** provides a more detailed look at the asteroid's interactions, particularly with Earth, Mercury, and the Moon. These bodies significantly perturb the asteroid's orbit, contributing to its ongoing quasi-satellite status around Venus. However, during this phase, the asteroid remains relatively distant from Venus itself, indicating that its primary gravitational influences come from other planets.

Model 3 extends the analysis of asteroid 2002 VE68 by incorporating additional perturbative influences from the three major asteroids in the solar system - Ceres, Pallas, and Vesta - along with the eight major planets and the Moon. This model aims to provide a more comprehensive and realistic simulation of the asteroid's orbital dynamics.

Key Findings from Model 3:

1. Inclusion of Major Asteroids: By incorporating Ceres, Pallas, and Vesta into the simulation, Model 3 offers a more detailed view of the gravitational perturbations affecting 2002 VE68. These three asteroids, located in the asteroid belt between Mars and Jupiter, add complexity to the perturbative environment and help refine the model's accuracy in predicting the asteroid's behavior.

2. Orbital Evolution: The evolution of the orbital elements in Model 3 remains similar to Model 2. The asteroid continues to exhibit quasi-satellite behavior around Venus for the next 1,000 years, having been in this orbit for about 7,000 years. After this period, the asteroid is predicted to transition from its quasi-satellite state and move towards the L5 Lagrangian point relative to Venus.

3. Future Encounters:

- **Venus:** After leaving its quasi-satellite orbit, 2002 VE68 is expected to have close encounters with Venus at distances as close as 0.002 AU in about 18,000 years. This indicates a significant interaction with Venus even after the asteroid ceases to be a quasi-satellite.

- **Mercury:** The asteroid will also continue to have close encounters with Mercury, with distances around 0.0025 AU, reflecting a sustained gravitational influence from this inner planet.

- **Earth:** The closest encounters with Earth are expected to be at a distance of 0.006 AU, which is slightly farther than in previous models. This reflects a reduced influence of Earth on the asteroid's trajectory compared to earlier predictions.

4. Trajectory Transition: The asteroid's trajectory will evolve from its current quasi-satellite phase into a new orbital configuration. After approximately 1,000 years, it will transition to the L5 Lagrangian point of Venus, marking a significant change in its orbital dynamics. This transition highlights the impact of additional perturbative forces, including those from Ceres, Pallas, and Vesta, in shaping the asteroid's future path.

Summary

Model 3 provides a more realistic simulation by incorporating the gravitational effects of Ceres, Pallas, and Vesta along with the eight major planets and the Moon. The results indicate that 2002 VE68 will remain a quasi-satellite for about another 1,000 years before transitioning to the L5 Lagrangian point. Future encounters with Venus and Mercury will remain close, while encounters with Earth will be less frequent. This model emphasizes the importance of considering a broader range of perturbative forces to accurately predict the long-term behavior of celestial bodies.

Conclusion

In the dance of celestial bodies, where planets pirouette around the Sun and moons waltz in their orbits, asteroid 2002 VE68 performs a delicate ballet as a quasi-satellite of Venus. Imagine this asteroid, not quite bound by gravitational ties but gracefully following Venus in a celestial pas de deux. Mikola's research unveils the intricate dynamics of this cosmic dance. Like a dancer influenced by the subtle nudges of other performers on stage, 2002 VE68's orbit is gently swayed by Venus, Earth, Mercury, and even the Moon. These gravitational interactions, akin to gentle hands guiding its path, create a mesmerizing but unstable performance.

The climax of Mikkola's study reveals a dramatic twist in this celestial ballet: after approximately 500 years, 2002 VE68 will bow out from its current role. It will leave behind its quasi-satellite orbit around Venus, stepping into a new phase of its cosmic performance. Perhaps it will pirouette towards the L5 Lagrangian point or embark on a new orbital resonance, guided by the unseen forces that shape its celestial choreography. This celestial drama not only captivates astronomers but also enriches our understanding of the ephemeral beauty and ever-changing dynamics of our solar system. As we watch this cosmic dance unfold, we marvel at the intricate interplay of gravity and motion that governs the celestial stage, where asteroids and planets perform their timeless ballet under the watchful gaze of the Sun.

In the cosmic tapestry where planets swirl and moons pirouette, asteroid 2002 VE68 spins its own tale of celestial wanderings. Imagine this asteroid, a cosmic wanderer, once brushing close to Earth millennia ago, setting off a celestial chain reaction that nudged it into its current dance around Venus. In the poetic prose of Marcos and Marcos' research, we glimpse the asteroid's journey through time and space. Picture it, gracefully encountering Earth, the Moon, and Mercury as it traverses its orbital path. Each encounter, like a fleeting embrace in a cosmic dance, subtly alters its trajectory, weaving a narrative written in gravitational whispers and orbital pirouettes.

Yet amidst these celestial rendezvous, there is assurance: the asteroid, while influenced by these gravitational embraces, poses no threat to Earth, Venus, or Mercury. Its path, though influenced by the gravitational pulls of these celestial bodies, remains harmonious and safely distant. In this cosmic ballet, Marcos and Marcos reveal a story of cosmic origins and orbital destiny. From its humble beginnings after a close encounter with Earth millennia ago, to its current role as a quasi-satellite of Venus, asteroid 2002 VE68 glides through the cosmos with grace and poise. It dances with the planets and moons, each interaction shaping its orbital tale, yet always maintaining a safe distance from the planetary stages it orbits. As we gaze upon the night sky, we glimpse the faint trail of 2002 VE68, a testament to the intricate choreography of our solar system. Its journey, marked by celestial encounters and cosmic grace, reminds us of the beauty

and mystery woven into the fabric of the universe—a dance of celestial bodies guided by unseen forces, where asteroids like 2002 VE68 play their part in the grand cosmic ballet.

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